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FACT SHEET: CommonsCasting 2035: Exploring a Future Intellectual Property, Data, and Knowledge Commons for Public AI Infrastructure

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Summary

The proposed project aims to investigate the potential for a future intellectual property (IP), data, and knowledge commons to support public infrastructure for research, information management, and innovation. Artificial intelligence (AI) capability is expanding at a rate incommensurate with the rate of adaptation of our IP and data infrastructure. Interest in productivity gains is now being replaced by actionable concern, manifesting in a variety of initiatives to address risks such as IP misuse, data-poisoning threats, and over-consolidation of AI capability. Resource-commons models have been proposed as a foundation for shared infrastructure, but implementation requires careful consideration of complex interconnections of incentives, rights, duties-of-care, and BOLTS (Business, Operations, Legal, Technical, Social) requirements. Proposed is the planning of a yearlong program to convene an interdisciplinary, multi-organization initiative to catalog resources, identify risks, opportunities, requirements, and remedies. As part of this initiative, participants would engage in a "ThreatCasting" exercise to explore and clarify what a functional future IP, data, and knowledge commons (and its absence) might look like. ThreatCasting methods will be adapted for "CommonsCasting", focused on social systems and legal engineering for distributed governance schemes. Key deliverables include a new CVE resource, an opportunity catalog, a technical report, and creative outputs.

Keywords: Intellectual Property; Legal Engineering; Requirements Engineering; AI; Data Infrastructure; Public AI; Creator Economy; Commons; Digital Commons; Governance; Risk Management; Data Empowerment; Data Access Management

V1.0

Background

Artificial intelligence (AI) capability and accessibility is growing at a rate incommensurate with the rate of adaptation of our intellectual property (IP), knowledge and information management, and data infrastructure. Interest in the novelty and productive gains offered by AI functions is being rapidly replaced by actionable concern, manifesting in (i) multiple movements within creative and intellectual communities to limit, boycott, or even poison the digital dissemination of their work due to a lack of adequate IP protection, enforcement, and attribution, (ii) research programs by government agencies to address the looming threats of data poisoning and behavior manipulation exacerbated by a lack of common provenance, interoperability, and professional and ethical standards for data management and dissemination, and (iii) a variety of new initiatives by nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) to reorient AI development away from a potential dystopian future.

Failure to address these phenomena will have real-world impacts, such as the potential for life-threatening errors in high reliability domains such as medicine and bioengineering. Further consequences could include potential for cultural centralization, homogenization, and exploitation, as well as impacts on national security, education, academic and public discourse, and democratic processes. These risks only intensify in combination with factors such as over-consolidation of compute, data access, and AI capability, model bias, lack of professional standards, and synthetic media. Resource commons and similar models for collective management of shared resources and risks enable a more resilient and sustainable sociotechnical infrastructure. Such models are currently under consideration by a variety of organizations and initiatives, however, there is a complex interplay of incentives, rights, responsibilities and duties of care, as well as business, operations, legal, technical, and social (BOLTS) requirements to consider that require thorough investigation and creative exploration prior to implementation.

Proposed is the planning of a 1-year, multi-phase program which will convene a radically diverse and interdisciplinary collection of subject matter experts to catalog resources and taxonomize key patterns of relevant risks, requirements, and remedies. The intended program will use "ThreatCasting" workshops that explore and clarify what a future IP, data, and knowledge commons (and its absence) might look like on a ten year horizon. This work will result in (i) a public common vulnerabilities and exploits (CVE) resource, (ii) a public common opportunities and innovations (COI) resource (iii) creative products which communicate possible implications and future scenarios, and (iv) a report with policy recommendations, descriptions of requirements and key threat and opportunity surfaces, next steps, and indicators of progress toward various defined scenarios. In addition to these outputs, the project's application and adaptation of the ThreatCasting methodology offers an opportunity to pioneer and test a "CommonsCasting" variant. This new approach would specifically focus on incorporating legal engineering and requirements engineering strategies to facilitate design of shared resource schemes.

Fact Sheet

Contained here is a Fact Sheet offering: background information on the underlying theoretical approach, context on the potential solution space and approach, details on the problems the work seeks to address, and definitions of key terms.

Resource Commons and Digital Commons Approaches

- A resource commons is a shared pool of resources that is collectively managed and governed by a community, allowing for equitable access and sustainable use. Best practices exist for management of a resource commons, the most well known of which are the 8 Principles for Commons Management:¹
 - Clearly defined boundaries of the commons, for instance, clear definitions of common resources, and under what conditions they can be accessed;
 - Rules set and tailored to the specific needs and circumstances of local users;
 - Implementation of mechanisms which enable participants in the commons to participate in modification of the rules;
 - Clarity in the extent of the commons' sovereignty - that the rules of the commons and the right of participants to modify them is respected by external authorities;
 - Implementation of mechanisms for self-monitoring and self-regulation, e.g., “neighborhood watch”;
 - Systems of escalating, or graduating sanctions and enforcement capability;
 - Access to low-cost mediation and conflict-resolution;
 - Use of a nested enterprise which ensures that provision and appropriation,² governance, mediation and conflict resolution, as well as enforcement activities and affordances are embedded in a multi-layer organizational structure.

¹ Hess C, Ostrom E. Understanding Knowledge as a Commons: From Theory to Practice. MIT Press; 2011.

² Provision and appropriation, in the context of a commons would refer, respectively, to the facilitation of resource access (i.e. how is the resource actually provided to the commons participant) and resource allocation (i.e. how is the resource actually allocated to participants or groups of participants and for what purposes or with what limitations).

- The use of resource-commons approaches to shared management of digital information assets is not new. Starting with the free software movement, “digital commons” approaches have played a pivotal role in shaping the internet. Among the most well-known examples are those concerned with knowledge (e.g., Wikipedia), IP (e.g., GNU and Creative Commons licensing schemes, and open-source software), and data (e.g., data commons, trusts, and cooperatives).
- The rapid development and proliferation of AI capabilities have introduced novel forms of IP misuse and new challenges; such as large language models replicating licensed content and the difficulty of detecting these infringements when they occur. Furthermore, the designers, developers, and operators (DDOs) of AI systems face unprecedented liability concerns, while new threat vectors such as data poisoning remain inadequately addressed by existing sociotechnical infrastructure. These risks, in combination with the potential overconsolidation of AI capability, training data, and compute in the hands of a small number of private firms, has led to a variety of initiatives proposing commons approaches that would support shared digital infrastructure to mitigate these risks. However, it remains unclear what a functional, appropriate commons would look like, and discussion (and critique) of its potential may be hindered by a few misconceptions, for example:
 - It is a common assumption that all resources contained addressed by a resource commons are simply equally available to, extractable by, consumable by, or owned by all participants. Such a situation is actually a description of the conditions for a “tragedy of the commons”, as introduced by biologist Garrett Hardin, i.e. a commons with no rules for access, coordination, and governance invites the over-exploitation or misuse of common resources to the detriment of the group. Furthermore, a resource commons does not necessarily require equal rights to access and use, there are many examples of resource commons which make use of tiered or role-based access and use-conditions dependent on a variety of factors.
 - It is often assumed that the resources being managed must be literally contained within the commons. However, a digital commons institution and its ruleset can facilitate the management of resources without enclosing them in a literal sense, such as by governing the licensing, access, and use of files not stored on the institution's hardware. Hence, a commons approach to IP and data management does not *necessarily* entail a storage requirement of IP and data.
- In the context of digital assets and IP, a resource commons supporting shared infrastructure could include shared data sets (e.g., training data), knowledge repositories, compute and analysis capabilities, models (e.g., large language models), and IP or stable references to these assets. Of higher importance however, is what it

might include in terms of provision, appropriation, governance, mediation and conflict resolution, as well as enforcement mechanisms and affordances relevant to that content. It is the management of rights, duties-of-care, stewardship, quality control, and the use and expectations of use—along with enforcement actions and sanctions for misuse—that would enable the commons to function as a foundation for shared (i.e., public) digital infrastructure. For example, digital assets or IP managed within a digital commons do not necessarily have to be “owned by” or “accessible to” all participants, but its reference data and access information might be. The stability of these meta-assets may in some cases be more valuable and impactful than universal accessibility of the resource itself.

- A resource commons for IP and digital assets requires careful consideration of business, operations, legal, technical, and social (BOLTS) requirements in order to avoid common patterns of commons risks, for example:
 - (i) **Free-rider problems**, where individuals benefit from resources without contributing to their maintenance or development;
 - (ii) **Overproduction or congestion**, where digital assets, while not depleted through use, see access problems caused by volume and poor routing;
 - (iii) **Underprovisioning**, where lack of sufficient contribution or investment in the commons leads to stagnation or decline in resource quality or availability;
 - (iv) **Pollution or degradation**, which in a digital commons could manifest as the introduction of low-quality data, malicious code, or deliberately poisoned information;
 - (v) **Enclosure or privatization**, where colluding entities attempt to inappropriately restrict access or appropriate common resources for private gain;
 - (vi) **Tower of Babel problems**, where poor coordination, communication, ontology, and standardization among users creates inefficient resource access or misuse;
 - (vii) **Tragedy of the anticommons**, where attempts to resolve incentives for contribution result in an imbalance of rights to exclude others from use, leading to accidental or inappropriate enclosure, inefficient use, underuse or misuse;
 - (viii) **Clique capture and regulatory capture**, where governance of the commons is influenced unduly by cliques and special interest groups at the expense of the broader community;

- (ix) **Scale mismatch**, where difficulties in managing resources arise when the scale of the resource system doesn't match the scale of its governance structures; and
- (x) **Trust, reputation, and confidence issues**, where misalignments between system state, capability, expectation, and representation undermine system effectiveness and participation.
- Joint efforts are needed to ensure effective governance of the collection, creation, use, and monetization of AI training data, in ways that promote interoperability, responsible management, privacy protection, empowerment, and rights enhancement.

Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE)

- Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures/Exploits (CVE) cataloging (or databasing) approaches are in common use in cybersecurity and similar disciplines for documenting, sharing, and coordinating response to and mitigation of common risks. CVE approaches can be generalized or adapted for other domains.
- The envisioned CVE catalog for this work would focus on common legal, economic, and social systems engineering risks related to resource commons approaches.

Common Opportunities and Innovations (COI)

- Where a CVE focuses on common reference and ontology of risks, threats, exposures, and coordination of remedy in a system across multiple organizations and stakeholders, a common opportunities and innovations catalog focuses on common reference and ontology of opportunities for development and growth, potential innovations, goals, and coordination of approach toward those goals.
- The envisioned COI catalog for this work would be structured to allow interoperability with COI resources managed by partner organizations.

Data Poisoning

- Data poisoning, in common use, refers to a broad set of methods and patterns of activity that result in the intentional degradation of the applied value of a data set. Common data poisoning methods include the introduction of noisy or altered data into training data sets, manipulation of data at 'watering holes' (i.e. locations where data will be collected), and manipulation of the metadata or context of the data (as opposed to the data itself). While usually used in the context of effects on machine learning solutions, data poisoning risks are relevant to statistics and data use in general, and may not always be implemented for malicious purposes.

- The use of data poisoning and its potential impacts are highly relevant to this work. This is because: (i) data poisoning methodologies pose serious risks and challenges to a digital commons, especially those requiring high reliability considerations³; (ii) commons-based approaches, paired with CVE methodologies, offer significant opportunities to reduce some data poisoning risks; and (iii) data poisoning is now also being used for non-malicious purposes, like defensive poisoning of digital assets to prevent their use in training data, and the effects of this strategy are not yet fully understood.

Advanced Social and Behavioral Engineering

- Recent advances in AI capability offer significantly advanced social and behavioral engineering capability and accessibility at scale to both commercial and threat actors. We do not have adequate infrastructure or tactics, techniques, and protocol (TTP) to address preservation of cognitive liberty⁴ and cognitive security⁵ in an environment where:
 - Commercial actors fail to establish shared professional and ethical standards, as well as common governance rules, for the use of AI and proprietary datasets in sophisticated targeting and tailoring of advertising, marketing, or pricing (e.g., based on individual preferences or real-time sentiment at the moment of ad delivery), exacerbating an already unsustainable information and predictive/forecasting asymmetry;
 - IP and similar assets (e.g., usage rights for fictional characters or publicity rights of celebrities), compute, and AI capability become overconsolidated within a small collection of firms, creating an unsustainable asymmetry in marketing capability; and

³ For example, data poisoning related to CBRN (Chemical, Biological, Radioactive, and Nuclear), medicine and public health, bioengineering, materials science, and control systems (e.g., industrial supervisory control and data acquisition [SCADA] systems), where very high levels of reliability are necessary to avoid catastrophic errors.

⁴ Cognitive Liberty is the notion of a right to cognitive self-determination; the freedom for an individual to have autonomy in deciding belief, conceptualization, and worldview without undue external coercion or intrusive manipulation. No one is free from influence, but where there is asymmetric information via intrusive surveillance and modeling, there may be a blurred line between, for example, advertising and offensive social engineering, or user retention strategies and dark patterns in user experience design which manipulate the user through hostile architecture.

⁵ Cognitive Security represents security in relation to cognition; the practices and methods intended to defend against social engineering attempts (i.e. intentional and unintentional manipulation of and disruptions to cognitive process and sensemaking) at any scale (e.g., personal, organizational, societal).

- State and threat actors can engage in sophisticated targeting, optimization, and tailoring of social and behavioral engineering tactics combined with near-realtime deepfaked audio and visual media at scale.

Risk of Cultural Centralization and Homogenization

- Algorithms for curation and recommendations now shape much of the internet's cultural landscape, often more than the creators themselves. While data-driven curation boosts engagement and content consumption, it's become increasingly questionable how much it improves content quality or how much it benefits the users and creators. Many creators openly admit they make creative choices not for their audience or artistic integrity, but to satisfy "the algorithm."
 - This raises risks of filter bubbles and cultural/ideological homogenization, further driven by content moderation and curation approaches on media dissemination. Such risks are becoming a common subject in public discourse.
- The advance and proliferation of AI capability for advanced, sophisticated targeting (or removal) of content, paired with the ability to generate or edit tailored content on demand, demands exploration of psychosocial implications, as well as business, operations, legal, and technical implications:
 - **Psychosocial:** AI systems, if trained on data owned or controlled by a small collection of corporations, will likely demonstrate a tendency to reflect the duties, interests, and preferences of those corporations and their psychographic/demographic base. Feedback loops can be formed where systems make use of user-data influenced by promotion and curation activity, increasingly marginalizing and filtering unconventional, currently unpopular, and untested aesthetic, narrative dynamics, and viewpoints. The psychological and social effects of this in this context have not been properly explored.
 - **Business:** Resolution of relevant risks likely requires participation by for-profit organizations and existing platforms. These risks can be framed not just as sociocultural risks, but also as sustainability and profitability risks for the platforms themselves which engage in curation. The potential relationship between resolving the problems discussed and its effects on curation efficacy and user experience, trust, and engagement have not been properly explored (e.g., maintaining cultural diversity by reducing centralization of generative capability may actually improve platform sustainability over the long term).

- **Operations/Technical:** The potential for state actors and opportunists to take advantage of centralized curation and data pipelines in order to perform novel forms of stochastic radicalization, narrative influence campaigns, or social engineering attacks (e.g., via data poisoning) has not been properly explored.
- **Legal:** Aggressive, automated enforcement deters creators from innovating or building upon existing ideas or disseminating their work, leading to a decrease in diversity and originality in creative outputs. Advancements in AI enable large corporations and entities with extensive IP portfolios to enforce their rights more extensively and aggressively by using automated systems for IP tracking and litigation, creating an imbalance of power with creators who lack the resources to defend their work. The impact of such capabilities over the long term has not been properly explored.
- The consolidation of AI capability, IP portfolios, and data sets within a small number of large firms poses a significant risk in creating an asymmetry in generative capabilities (as well as targeting of that generative capability).
- Without the ability to "create off the shoulders of others" or take risks in creating content that might be similar to existing content, the creative landscape becomes more uniform, reducing the variety of choices available to the public and hindering cultural and technological advancement. Practical measures are needed to support cultural and linguistic diversity as well as safeguard indigenous knowledge and cultural expression.
- Inclusion of digital content in training data sets without auditability has created a variety of new dynamics which limit sharing of work and innovation and contribute to marginalization of non-corporate actors:
 - **Boycotting Dissemination and Publishing:** There are a number of artists who are publicly announcing boycotts of public sharing of their work due to IP misuse, unlicensed use of their work in AI models, and lack of enforcement capability.
 - **Defensive Data Poisoning:** This refers to the purposeful poisoning of a digital asset to combat classification activity and use as training data. In the short term, this serves as a viable strategy to limit IP misuse, but in the long term, it may present a wide range of problems for historical and cultural archiving, classification, collection, and curation activities.

ThreatCasting

- Threatcasting is a method for envisioning and planning for future scenarios, particularly in the context of emerging threats and opportunities. It is especially useful in fields dealing with rapid or volatile technological change.⁶
- This methodology generally consists of a core team that facilitates workshops and prepares materials, a steering committee of stakeholders and subject matter experts to assist, and a wider group of participants.
- Threatcasting helps organizations anticipate future threats and opportunities and develop actionable plans for detection and mitigation.
- Threatcasting focuses on longer-term horizons (generally 10+ years) and incorporates a wider range of societal and technological factors than traditional scenario-design methods. It also uses exploratory and creative exercises to harness and communicate the insight and imagination of participating subject matter experts, while still providing the kinds of technical reports familiar to traditional organizations.
- ThreatCasting is implemented in the following phases:
 - Phase 0 – **Preparation and Curation (Pre-Workshop)**: (i) Develop Threatcasting Foundation: topic area, research question, and application areas, (ii) Curate team, participants, and research prompts, and (iii) Prepare workshop materials.
 - Phase 1 – **Prompt Presentation, Research Synthesis, and Discussion (Workshop)**: (i) Present prompts to participants, (ii) Engage in participatory design session, and (iii) Capture discussions in workbooks.
 - Phase 2 – **Futurecasting (Workshop)**: (i) Envision potential threats 10 years in the future, (ii) Use science fiction prototyping and experience design Processes, and (iii) Generate qualitative Effect-Based Model (EBM).
 - Phase 3 – **Backcasting (Workshop)**: (i) Develop Time-phased, Alternative-action Definition (TAD), (ii) Generate actions to disrupt, mitigate, and recover from threats, (iii) Identify indicators (flags) of emerging threats, and (iv) Repeat Phases 2 and 3 to generate multiple threat futures.
 - Phase 4 – **Post Analysis, Synthesis, and Findings (Post Workshop)**: (i) Analyze raw data from workbooks, (ii) Cluster and identify possible threats and opportunities, (iii) Document findings and conduct peer review, and (iv) Perform additional research if needed.

⁶ Johnson BD, Vanatta N, Coon C. Threatcasting. Morgan & Claypool; 2021

- Phase 5 – **Output (Post Workshop)**: (i) Translate findings into appropriate output format, (ii) Determine output based on Threatcasting Foundation, and (iii) Tailor output to the needs of the stakeholders

The methodology will be expanded to include the forecasting of opportunities in addition to threats.

Potential ThreatCasting Prompts

Exploration of a potential Phase 0 (pre-workshop) activity resulted in the following prompts for consideration:

- How might IP evolve into a more openly shared resource among creators and innovators by 2035, while still providing incentives for creation?
- Are there historical examples of information commons? How did they operate? What were their features? How did they end?
- What new models of governance and collective decision-making for IP, data, and knowledge management could emerge in the next decade, balancing individual rights with community benefits?
- How might overprotection or underutilization of IP lead to a 'tragedy of the anticommons' by 2035, and what are potential solutions?
- In what ways might IP governance systems need to adapt by 2035 to accommodate rapid technological changes and global challenges? Is it possible without rip-and-replace of existing IP and data infrastructure?
- How could the ease of digital reproduction reshape the concept of IP ownership and access by 2035?
- What would it look like if an IP, data, and knowledge commons was successfully captured or poisoned by colluding threat actors, opportunists, or an oppressive regime?
- What new kinds of art, information, and conceptual exploration become possible with a successful information commons?
- How might an IP, data, and knowledge commons enhance innovation potential and create opportunities for development and growth?

Future Work and Next Steps

By December 2024, the initial members of the team will convene a core cadre of performers representative of a diverse set of disciplines and backgrounds. The intention is to include at least one member for each of the following organizational categories of interest: small firms, universities, freelance or independent contractors, government agencies, NGOs, large firms, and community labs. This initial team will include experts in legal and technical requirements engineering, commons approaches, mechanism and market design, social systems engineering, wargaming, and the ThreatCasting framework. Following the formation of this team, next steps consist of:

- Initializing a common information management system and setting a weekly meeting for team members.
- Forming a “big-list” of potential participants and their backgrounds, and potential members of the steering committee.
- Performance of Phase 0 of the ThreatCasting Framework (i.e. (i) refining the topic area, research questions, and areas of application, (ii) refining the big-list into an invitation list, and finalization of prompts, and (iii) preparation of workshop materials.
- Preparation and consensus on an approach to CVE and COI development, and scoping of resource collection throughout.
- Preparation of Phases 1-5 of the ThreatCasting program and a workshop plan, including a clear timeline, budget, basis of estimate, deliverables breakdown, letters of commitment from the core team and their organizations, letters of commitment from members of the Steering Committee, and letters of support from potential workshop participants and supporting organizations.
- Integration of Phase 0 and other relevant planning materials into a funding proposal prepared for several potential sponsors, to ensure there are reasonable resources, host venues, and auspices for workshop and planning activities.

Document History

Date	Version	Memo
10/28/2024	1.0	Initial Release